

Chemical and Spectroscopic Studies in Metal β -Diketonates: Part VII. Electronic Spectral Studies on Al(III), Cu(II) and Pd(II)-1,3- Diketonates* and their γ -Substituted Derivatives

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Electronic absorption spectra of solutions of Al(III), Cu(II) and Pd(II) β -diketonate chelates have been measured in the 200–800 m μ region. The spectral data have been interpreted in terms of the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ and other transitions and the effects of chelate ring substituents at γ -position on the different transitions determined. Substitution of halogens results in a bathochromic shift of $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transition in each chelate, perhaps due to extension of conjugation. The hypsochromic shifts observed in the cases of $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{SCN}$ γ -substituents are supposed to be due to the prevention of coplanarity of these groups with the chelate ring by the two flanking methyl groups in metal 1,3-diketonates (Steric inhibition of resonance). An absorption band at ~ 340 m μ obtained in $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_2\text{-acac})_3$ has been interpreted as being due to intramolecular charge-transfer similar to that observed in nitro benzene. The replacement of methyl groups by phenyl groups in $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n$ shifts the absorption bands towards lower energy in all the transitions, indicating the dominance of the resonance effect over the weak inductive effect of the phenyl ring. Thus, shifts to lower energy in the order, $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n > \text{M}(\text{bzac})_n > \text{M}(\text{dbm})_n$ are observed.

Halogenation¹, nitration^{2–4}, thiocyanation⁵, acetylation⁶ and formylation⁶ reactions of metal 1,3-diketonates carried out under electrophilic substitution reaction conditions analogous to those of electrophilic aromatic substitution have been reported by us earlier. In view of the observed extension of conjugation on halogenation of these chelates at the central carbon atom, during preliminary electronic spectral studies¹, we extended the electronic spectral investigations to acetylacetonates, benzoylacetonates and dibenzoylmethanates of Al(III), Cu(II) and Pd(II) and to their derivatives carrying $-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{Br}$, $-\text{NO}_2$, and $-\text{SCN}$ substituents at the central carbon atom (γ -position) of each chelate ring (I). The spectral

* acac = acetylacetonate; bzac = benzoylacetonate; dbm = dibenzoylmethanate.

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data thus obtained are potentially useful for better understanding of the so far controversial electronic structure of the so called quasi-aromatic β -diketonate chelate rings.

$R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$; acetylacetonate

$R_1 = \text{CH}_3$, $R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; benzoylacetonate

$R_1 = R_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; dibenzoylmethanate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Materials: All the metal 1,3-diketonates and their derivatives used in the present investigation were prepared and purified as reported by us earlier¹⁻⁵. All the solvents employed were of AnalaR grade (BDH), dried and redistilled before use.

Spectral Measurements: All spectra were measured at 25° on a Cary Model 14R spectrophotometer in the 200–800 $m\mu$ region using 1 cm. quartz cells. The concentration of the solutions used were in the range $10^{-2}M$ – $10^{-5}M$ ($\sim 10^{-2}M$, visible; $10^{-5}M$ ultraviolet regions). These were first made upto $\sim 10^{-1}M$ by weight using an analytical balance and then diluted to the desired concentrations with appropriate solvent. Extinction coefficients were calculated from $\epsilon = (\log I_0/I)/\text{molarity}$. The reproducibility of the ϵ values was found in general to be within $\sim 5\%$. Wavelengths given are reliable to $\pm 1 m\mu$.

RESULTS AND BAND ASSIGNMENTS

The significant peaks in the absorption spectra of the metal complexes studied and their possible assignments are recorded in Tables I–III. The general trend of the absorption spectra of divalent and trivalent metal benzoylacetonates and dibenzoylmethanates is quite similar to those of the corresponding metal acetylacetonates. Therefore, the results of the

Huckel LCAO-MO calculation carried out by Barnum⁷ and Fackler et al.^{8,9} are generally referred to in the assignment of absorption bands in our work.

TABLE I

Absorption Bands in Al(III) β -Diketonates and its γ -Substituted Derivatives

R_1	R_2	γ	Solvent	λ_{max} (m μ); log ϵ		
				$\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$		
CH ₃	CH ₃	H	CHCl ₃ EtOH	—	288; 4.582	—
					287; 4.61	
CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	CHCl ₃ EtOH	—	290; 4.42	—
					289; 4.45	
CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	CHCl ₃ EtOH	—	305; 4.48	—
					304; 4.50	
CH ₃	CH ₃	NO ₂	CHCl ₃ EtOH	—	284; 4.51	341; 3.23
					282; 4.50	340; 3.25
CH ₃	CH ₃	CNS	CHCl ₃ EtOH	—	283; 4.475	—
					280; 4.48	
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	H	CHCl ₃	250; 3.95	320; 4.30	—
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	CHCl ₃	260; 4.14	311; 4.18	(345)
C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	CHCl ₃	258; 4.16	348; 4.65	—
C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	CHCl ₃	258; 4.32	334; 4.59	(350)

Shoulder bands are enclosed in parentheses.

Aluminium Complexes: From Table I, it is apparent that the γ -substituents, except NO₂ and SCN, tend to shift the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transition band to a longer wavelength with respect to Al(acac)₃. An absorption band at ~ 340 m μ obtained in the case of γ -NO₂ substituent only (Fig. 1), has been tentatively interpreted as being due to intramolecular charge-transfer similar to that observed in nitro-benzene¹⁰⁻¹². When methyl groups are successively replaced by phenyl groups in Al(acac)₃, a new band at ~ 260 m μ appears. Presumably, this is due to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ secondary band (¹L_b) of the benzene ring.

Copper Complexes: The spectra of Cu(acac)₂ and its γ -substituted complexes are generally similar, which may be discussed in terms of the five clearly separated bands I—V (Table II). In no case, it was possible to observe the high energy band I with the γ -substituted derivatives because of their limited solubility in cyclohexane. The position of band II is found to vary only slightly with changes in the γ -substituent but band III shifts

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markedly to longer wavelengths with increasing ortho-para directing capabilities (towards benzene) of the group.

FIG. 1—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF :
 ——— $Al(acac)_3$ IN CHLOROFORM
 - - - $Al(NO_2-acac)_3$ IN CHLOROFORM

TABLE II

Absorption Bands in Cu(II) β -Diketonates and its γ -Substituted Derivatives

R_1	R_2	γ	Solvent	λ_{max} (m μ); log ϵ				
				Band I $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_5$	Band II	Band III $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$	Band IV	Band V
			$CHCl_3$	—	246; 4.20	296; 4.415	560; 1.50	670; 1.56
CH_3	CH_3	H	CH_3OH	—	241; 4.19	294; 4.40	—	—
			C_6H_{12}	201; 4.19	245; 4.26	297; 4.38	—	—
CH_3	CH_3	Cl	$CHCl_3$	—	—	312; 4.44	(540)	670; 1.61
CH_3	CH_3	Br	$CHCl_3$	—	248; 4.190	308; 4.415	—	670; 1.62
CH_3	CH_3	NO_2	$CHCl_3$	—	246; 4.08	294; 4.450	—	645; 1.77
CH_3	CH_3	SCN	$CHCl_3$	—	245; 4.140	294; 4.43	—	645; 1.77
CH_3	C_6H_5	H	CH_3OH	—	250; 3.85	320; 4.322	640; 1.70	(680); 1.67
C_6H_5	C_6H_5	H	Dioxane	—	260; 3.28	350; 4.58	650; 1.88	(685); 1.86

Shoulder bands are enclosed in parentheses.

TABLE III

*Absorption Bands in Pd(II) β -Diketonates and its γ -Substituted Derivatives**

R_1	R_2	γ	λ_{max} (m μ); log ϵ			
			Band I	Band II	Band III	Band IV
CH ₃	CH ₃	H	250; 4.53	(260–270)	330; 4.380	(400); 2.47
CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	—	(260–270)	345; 4.09	—
CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	—	(260–270)	345; 3.94	—
CH ₃	CH ₃	NO ₂	250; 4.322	(260–270)	328; 4.049	—
CH ₃	CH ₃	SCN	250; 4.310	(260–270)	327; 4.05	—
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	H	260; 4.70	285; 4.69	352; 4.49	—
CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	NO ₂	260; 4.62	284; 4.70	348; 4.36	—
C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	265; 4.80	300; 4.74	372; 4.50	405; 4.301

* All spectra have been recorded in chloroform solvent.
Shoulder bands are enclosed in parentheses.

Bands I and III are assigned as $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_5$ and $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transitions respectively. Barnum has suggested that band II may be a component of the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transition⁷. However, a more likely assignment now seems to be as a charge-transfer band involving the jump of a σ -bonding or oxygen n -electron to a metal orbital⁸. The only orbitals which seem likely as the acceptor orbitals on the copper ion are the vacant $4p_z$ and the half-filled $3d_{xy}$. Fackler et. al.⁹, on the basis of solvent effect, argued that $3d_{xy}$ rather than $4p_z$ is the acceptor orbital. Moreover, the absence of any pronounced effect of γ -substituents on the energy of band II supports the view that the electron which is "transferred", originates in a σ or n orbital rather than a π -orbital, since γ -substitution has a marked effect upon π -orbitals.

Lately, there has been considerable interest concerning the assignments of bands IV and V, appearing in the visible region of the spectrum of Cu(acac)₂. Solvent effects¹³ and polarizations^{14–16} as well as inferences from electron spin resonance¹⁷ data have been invoked to make assignments. No final solution to the problem has yet appeared but the paper of Piper and Belford¹⁵ presents the current position. The data obtained in this work themselves, do not throw much further light on the question, though the shift of both bands IV and V to lower energies with decreasing inductive character of the α -substituents is consistent with the assumption that d_{xy} is the orbital of highest energy.

Palladium Complexes: Table III lists the wavelengths of maximum absorption and intensities observed for Pd(II) β -diketonates and its γ -substituted derivatives. Bands I, II and III are somewhat similar, all showing up as most intense bands at 250–265 m μ and less intense bands at 330–372 m μ (band III). In addition, other less intense bands are observed in the region 260–300 m μ . The γ -substituents have strong effect on band III, showing bathochromic shift.

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DISCUSSION

$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ *Ligand Transitions* : The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the ligand in different γ -substituted metal acetylacetonates is expected to shift in a manner similar to spectral shifts observed in substituted benzenes¹⁸, if the chelate ring system is quasi-aromatic in nature. However, the hypsochromic shifts observed for the γ -nitro- and γ -cyano derivatives indicate that no such simple comparison could be made. The 260 $m\mu$ $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in benzene always shifts to lower energies with ring substitution. It is evident that in the case of each metal β -diketonate studied, only halogenation resulted in the shift of λ_{max} of $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transition towards longer wavelengths. It is also evident from the ultraviolet data on the unsubstituted and substituted chelates that halogenation in each case results in the increase of π -electron delocalization in the ring, thereby extending the conjugation. The hypsochromic shifts observed in the cases of $-\text{NO}_2$ and $-\text{SCN}$, γ -substituents are perhaps due to the prevention of coplanarity of these groups with the chelate ring by the two flanking methyl or phenyl groups in metal β -diketonates, thus sterically inhibiting resonance with the ring.

The π -orbitals in a $\text{M}(\text{acac})_3$ complex are triply degenerate, each of the three pairs of electrons being on a separate chelate ring¹⁹. Since they are so far apart, the repulsion between them and hence the magnitude of any splitting of the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ absorption band is expected to be much smaller than in benzene where the degenerate orbitals are on the same ring¹⁸. However, with increasing metal-ligand π -interaction, the repulsion between electrons in different rings should increase. This may be the reason for the apparent splitting of the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transition that is often observed. For example in $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$, $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4$ and many other complexes in which π -interaction is very weak, if it occurs at all, a slight shoulder appears on the long wave-length side of the $\pi_3 \rightarrow \pi_4$ band.

Effect of Replacing Methyl Groups by Phenyl Groups on Different Transitions of Metal Acetylacetonates : It is evident from the data in Tables I-III that the replacement of methyl groups by phenyl groups in metal acetylacetonates investigated, results in shifts of absorption bands towards lower energy in all transitions, indicating the dominance of the resonance effect over the weak inductive effect of the phenyl ring. Thus, shifts to lower energy in the order $\text{M}(\text{acac})_n > \text{M}(\text{bzac})_n > \text{M}(\text{dbm})_n$ are observed. Very recently, such shifts were also noticed by Sasaki et al.²⁰, when methyl group was replaced by furoyl ring in metal acetylacetonates.

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